

FLEXIBLE NONUNIFORM FILTER BANKS USING ALLPASS TRANSFORMATION OF MULTIPLE ORDER

M. Kappelan, B. Strauß, P. Vary

Institute of Communication Systems and Data Processing (IND)

RWTH Aachen, University of Technology

D-52056 Aachen, Germany

Tel: +49 (0)241 80 6959; Fax: +49 (0)241 8888 186

e-mail: kiwi@ind.rwth-aachen.de

ABSTRACT

This paper deals with allpass frequency transformations of uniform filter banks to achieve nonuniform bandwidths. The known transformation with an allpass of first order [1] [4] [5] [6] is extended to an allpass transformation of order K . Thus the flexibility of the filter bank design can be increased significantly.

1 INTRODUCTION

In this contribution the polyphase realization of the uniform FIR filter bank is generalized towards a nonuniform frequency resolution. The proposed approach is an extension of the well known allpass transformation of first order [1] [4] [5] by introducing an allpass of order K . The frequency transformation of the filter characteristics is achieved by replacing the delay elements of the FIR filter bank by identical recursive allpasses. A causal allpass of order K would create a filter bank with multiple images of the original (bandpass) filters, which can of course be useful e.g. for the design of comb filters [3]. Here a new phase compensation technique is introduced which avoids the multiple mapping of the frequency axis and therefore gives an increased design flexibility by using an allpass of order K .

2 UNIFORM FILTER BANK

Filter banks with uniform frequency resolution can be implemented very efficiently using a polyphase network (PPN) and the Fast Fourier Transformation (e.g. [5]). There are two equivalent versions which can be described by using either complex modulators with uniformly spaced frequencies and identical lowpasses or modulated bandpass filters which have been derived from a common prototype lowpass. Here, the latter version will be considered. If the impulse response of the FIR prototype lowpass is denoted by $w_0(n)$, the complex bandpass impulse responses with the center frequencies $\Omega_\mu = 2\pi\mu/N$ ($\mu = 0 \dots N-1$) are given by

$$w_\mu(n) = w_0(n)e^{+j\frac{2\pi}{N}\mu n} \quad \mu = 0 \dots N-1 \quad (1)$$

The subband signal of the μ 'th channel of the uniform filter bank can be described by

$$y_\mu(n) = x(n) * w_\mu(n) \quad (2)$$

where x is the input signal and $*$ denotes convolution (see fig. 1).

Figure 1: Reference model of the μ 'th channel of a uniform bandpass filter bank

For simplicity it is assumed that an N -tap FIR prototype lowpass $w_0(n)$ is used¹. In this case (eq. 2) reads

$$y_\mu(n) = \sum_{\nu=0}^{N-1} \underbrace{x(n-\nu)w_0(\nu)}_{x_\nu(n)} e^{+j\frac{2\pi}{N}\mu\nu} \quad (3a)$$

$$= \sum_{\nu=0}^{N-1} x_\nu(n) e^{+j\frac{2\pi}{N}\mu\nu} \quad (3b)$$

$$= \text{IDFT}\{x_\nu(n)\} \quad (3c)$$

Thus the set of samples $y_\mu(n)$ (n =fixed, $\mu = 0 \dots N-1$) can be calculated efficiently using the Inverse Fast Fourier Transformation (IFFT). If we introduce the z -domain version of $x_\nu(n)$ according to

$$X_\nu(z) = X(z)z^{-\nu}w_0(\nu) \quad (4)$$

we obtain the subband signals in the z -domain

$$Y_\mu(z) = \sum_{\nu=0}^{N-1} X_\nu(z)e^{+j\frac{2\pi}{N}\mu\nu} \quad (5)$$

as shown in fig. 2:

¹This approach can easily be extended to prototype filters with more than N taps.

Figure 2: IFFT implementation of a uniform filter bank ($N=8$)

The effective frequency responses are:

$$H_\mu(z) = Y_\mu(z)/X(z) = \sum_{\nu=0}^{N-1} w_0(\nu) z^{-\nu} e^{+j\frac{2\pi}{N}\mu\nu} \quad (6)$$

On the unit circle i.e. for $z = e^{j\Omega}$ we obtain the following transfer functions

$$H_0(e^{j\Omega}) = \sum_{\nu=0}^{N-1} w_0(\nu) e^{-j\nu\Omega} \quad (\text{prototype filter}) \quad (7)$$

$$H_\mu(e^{j\Omega}) = H_0(e^{j(\Omega - \frac{2\pi}{N}\mu)}) \quad (8)$$

The frequency responses of this uniform prototype filter bank given by (eq. 8) are shown in fig. 3 by example.

Figure 3: Uniform filter bank with allpass transformation of order $K = 1$, $a = 0$ (delay), $N = 32$, $\mu = 0, 4, 8, 12, 16$

3 GENERALIZED FILTER BANK

The filter structure of fig. 2 is generalized as shown in fig. 4 by replacing the delay elements by identical allpass filters $A(z)$ and by replacing the constant weights $w_0(\nu)$ by $B_\nu(z)$ ($\nu = 0 \dots N-1$).

Figure 4: Generalized filter bank using IDFT ($N = 8$)

The generalized IDFT (IFFT) filter bank structure is described by:

$$Y_\mu(z) = \sum_{\nu=0}^{N-1} X_\nu(z) e^{+j\frac{2\pi}{N}\mu\nu} \quad (9)$$

$$= \sum_{\nu=0}^{N-1} X(z) B_\nu(z) [A(z)]^\nu e^{+j\frac{2\pi}{N}\mu\nu} \quad (10)$$

The N outputs ($\mu = 0 \dots N-1$) of the filter bank in fig. 4 are now characterized by their transfer functions:

$$H_\mu(z) = \frac{Y_\mu(z)}{X(z)} = \sum_{\nu=0}^{N-1} B_\nu(z) [A(z)]^\nu e^{+j\frac{2\pi}{N}\mu\nu} \quad (11)$$

3.1 Uniform Filter Bank As Special Case

A special case of (eq. 11) is obviously the well known uniform polyphase filter bank (eq. 8) with the prototype filter (eq. 7) if we choose

$$A(z) = z^{-1} \quad B_\nu(z) = w_0(\nu) \quad (12)$$

3.2 Allpass Transformation Of First Order

The substitution of delay elements z^{-1} in (eq. 12) by the causal and stable allpass of order $K = 1$ with the complex parameter $\underline{a} = ae^{j\alpha}$ with $|\underline{a}| < 1$ leads to:

$$A(z) = A_1(z) = \frac{1 - \underline{a}^* z}{z - \underline{a}} \quad B_\nu(z) = w_0(\nu) \quad (13)$$

with

$$A_1(e^{j\Omega}) = e^{+j\varphi_1(\Omega)} \quad \text{and} \quad (14)$$

$$\varphi_1(\Omega) = -\Omega - 2 \arctan \frac{a \sin(\Omega - \alpha)}{1 - a \cos(\Omega - \alpha)} \quad (15)$$

which is the known nonuniform frequency transformation of the uniform filter bank of (eq. 8), describing the frequency responses:

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{H}_\mu(e^{j\Omega}) &= \sum_{\nu=0}^{N-1} w_0(\nu) e^{+j\frac{2\pi}{N}\nu\mu} e^{+j\nu\varphi_1(\Omega)} \\ &= H_\mu(e^{-j\varphi_1(\Omega)}) \\ &= H_0(e^{+j(-\varphi_1(\Omega) - \frac{2\pi}{N}\mu)})\end{aligned}\quad (16)$$

Generally speaking, the negative phase characteristic of the allpass describes the frequency transformation of the uniform prototype filter bank. In fig. 5 the negative phase of an allpass of first order ($a = 0.5$) and in fig. 6 the corresponding nonuniform filter bank transfer functions are plotted.

3.3 Allpass Transformation Of Higher Order With Multiple Mapping

The substitution of delay elements z^{-1} in (eq. 12) by a causal and stable allpass of order K with the complex parameters $\underline{a}_k = a_k e^{j\alpha_k}$ with $|\underline{a}_k| < 1$, $k = 1 \dots K$ and the prototype filter of (eq. 7) leads to:

$$\begin{aligned}A(z) &= A_K(z) = e^{j\alpha_0} \prod_{k=1}^K \frac{1 - a_k e^{-j\alpha_k} z}{z - a_k e^{j\alpha_k}} \\ A_K(e^{j\Omega}) &= e^{+j\varphi_K(\Omega)} \quad B_\nu(z) = w_0(\nu)\end{aligned}\quad (17)$$

with the phase of this allpass:

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_K(\Omega) &= \alpha_0 - K\Omega \\ &- 2 \sum_{k=1}^K \arctan \frac{a_k \sin(\Omega - \alpha_k)}{1 - a_k \cos(\Omega - \alpha_k)}\end{aligned}\quad (18)$$

It can be shown that the phase φ_K (eq. 18) of an **causal** stable allpass of order K of $A_K(z)$ (eq. 17) is monotone decreasing [2]. Thus the (2π periodic) frequency interval $[-K\pi; K\pi]$ of the prototype filter is mapped to the interval $[-\pi; \pi]$. This is equivalent to multiple compressed mapping of $[-\pi; \pi]$ of the prototype filter to the target range $[-\pi; \pi]$ as proposed in [3] for the design of comb filters.

3.4 Allpass Transformation Of Higher Order With Single Mapping

In order to exploit the enhanced flexibility of the allpass of order K but to avoid multiple mappings, the phase has to be limited to $[-\pi; \pi]$. This can be achieved by reducing the linear term $K\Omega$ in (eq. 18) to Ω , resulting in a **non causal** stable allpass $\hat{A}_K(z)$ (eq. 20) with a phase $\hat{\varphi}_K$ (eq. 19):

$$\hat{\varphi}_K(\Omega) = \varphi_K(\Omega) + (K-1)\Omega \quad (19)$$

$$\hat{A}_K(z) = z^{+(K-1)} A_K(z) \quad (20)$$

To avoid frequency reversions in the resulting filter structure, the phase $\hat{\varphi}_K(\Omega)$ of the **non causal** allpass has to be monotone decreasing which leads to the group delay constraint (eq. 21) of the allpass $A_K(z)$ (eq. 17).

$$-\frac{d}{d\Omega} \varphi_K(\Omega) = \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{1 - a_k^2}{1 - 2a_k \cos(\Omega - \alpha_k) + a_k^2} \stackrel{!}{>} K-1 \quad (21)$$

An example of allpass parameters which achieve a decreasing phase $\hat{\varphi}_K(\Omega)$ is shown for $K = 2$ in fig. 5 in comparison to the first order transformation characteristic $\varphi_1(\Omega)$. This demonstrates the enhanced flexibility in designing the nonuniform frequency transformation. The allpass of order $K = 2$ with conjugated complex parameters can be implemented by a network with real valued arithmetic.

3.5 Implementation

With (eq. 11) there are **non causal** implementations which have the same transfer functions:

$$A(z) = \underbrace{\hat{A}_K(z)}_{\text{non causal}} \quad B_\nu(z) = w_0(\nu) \quad (22a)$$

$$A(z) = \underbrace{A_K(z)}_{\text{causal}} \quad B_\nu(z) = \underbrace{z^{+(K-1)\nu} w_0(\nu)}_{\text{non causal}} \quad (22b)$$

$\nu = 0, 1 \dots N-1$

If the **non causal** part is shifted to $B_\nu(z)$ according to (eq. 22b), a **causal** implementation is possible by introducing an additional delay of $z^{-(K-1)(N-1)}$ resulting in:

$$\begin{aligned}A(z) &= A_K(z) \quad \nu = 0, 1 \dots N-1 \\ B_\nu(z) &= z^{-(K-1)(N-1-\nu)} w_0(\nu)\end{aligned}\quad (23)$$

The frequency response of this transformed **causal** transformed filter bank now reads:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{H}_\mu(e^{j\Omega}) &= e^{-j(N-1)(K-1)\Omega} \\ &\cdot \sum_{\nu=0}^{N-1} w_0(\nu) e^{+j\frac{2\pi}{N}\nu\mu} e^{+j\nu\hat{\varphi}_K(\Omega)} \\ &= e^{-j(N-1)(K-1)\Omega} H_\mu(e^{-j\hat{\varphi}_K(\Omega)}) \\ &= e^{-j(N-1)(K-1)\Omega} H_0(e^{+j(-\hat{\varphi}_K(\Omega) - \frac{2\pi}{N}\mu)})\end{aligned}\quad (24)$$

The block diagram is given in fig. 4

4 EXAMPLE AND CONCLUSIONS

The frequency responses of the compensated nonuniform filter bank for e.g. $K = 2$ are shown in fig. 7 revealing the enhanced flexibility of the new approach. In comparison to the transformation of order $K = 1$ as shown in fig. 6 the frequency resolution can now be increased e.g. within a bandpass interval. Thus the filter structure allows more parameters to design nonuniform filter banks using a common prototype FIR filter.

Figure 5: Frequency transformation with allpass of order $K = 1$ ($a_1 = 0, a_1 = 0.5$) and allpass with order $K = 2$ with conjugate complex coefficients ($a_1 = -0.5j, a_2 = +0.5j$) with compensation of the non causal phase

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Figure 6: Nonuniform filter bank with allpass transformation of order $K = 1, a = 0.5, N = 32, \mu = 0, 4, 8, 12, 16$

Figure 7: Nonuniform filter bank with allpass transformation of order $K = 2$ and compensation of the non causal phase ($a_1 = -0.5j, a_2 = +0.5j$), $N = 32, \mu = 0, 4, 8, 12, 16$